

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF FRP-CONFINED CONCRETE COLUMNS UNDER AXIAL COMPRESSIVE LOAD

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Keywords: Concrete columns, composite confinement, strength, deformability, stability

Abstract

The strength, deformability and stability of concrete columns confined by carbon composite sheets is considered at axial compressive loading. The formulas for prediction of ultimate strength, ultimate strain, and the tangent modulus above the limit of nonlinearity are given. Confined reinforced concrete columns also are considered.

The loss of stability of columns above the strength of plain concrete is analyzed and it is proved that FRP confinement is efficient only for columns having low or moderate slenderness ($\lambda < 40$).

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites have found wide applications in the civil engineering due to their high corrosion resistance and the ease of application. One important application of the fiber-reinforced composites is as confinement of the concrete columns to enhance the strength and ductility. Such confinement can be used when the strength of concrete structure should be improved (for damaged structures or for increased service load).

It is well observed by many researchers that the confined concrete above the ultimate compressive strength of the plain concrete f_{co} continues to carry the increased load, but in the bilinear manner with a second tangent modulus $E_2 \ll E_1$ (Figure 1).

The behavior of the confined concrete is characterized by the following quantities:

- E_1 initial elastic modulus of the concrete;
- f_{co} ultimate compressive strength of the plain concrete, which coincides with the limit of nonlinearity of the confined specimens;

- f_{cc} compressive strength of the confined concrete;
- E_2 tangent modulus the confined concrete after axial stress exceeds f_{co} ;
- ε_{cc} ultimate axial strain of the confined concrete.

Different formulas have been proposed for prediction of σ_{cc} and ε_{cc} . Less attention has been paid to value of E_2 .

Fig. 1. Cyclic axial stress – strain curve of the confined concrete specimens.

In the present report the results concerning strength, deformability, and stability of confined concrete columns obtained during the last years in the Institute of Polymer Mechanics of University of Latvia are summarized. These results have been published in the series of papers in journal Mechanics of Composite Materials [1-6].

- 1) In 2006 the formula for the strength f_{cc} of confined concrete column was analyzed:

$$f_{cc} = f_{co} + \frac{4\sigma_{ju}h}{R}, \quad (1)$$

where R is the radius of column, h - thickness of composite confinement, σ_{ju} - ultimate tensile

strength of composite, "jacket" which should be determined very carefully [2].

2) The formula for the modulus E_2 (Figure 1) was obtained in [3]

$$E_2 = 24 E_{lat} \cdot \left(\frac{f_{co}}{E_{lat}} \right)^{0.65}, \quad (2)$$

where $E_{lat} = E_j \frac{h}{R}$ is the "lateral modulus", but

E_j – modulus of composite jacket.

The formula (2) was derived analyzing the expression for nondimensional differential

Poisson's coefficient $\nu_d = \frac{\Delta \varepsilon_{lat}}{\Delta \varepsilon_z}$ as function of

the only nondimensional parameter of strength of confined concrete column $\frac{f_{co}}{E_{lat}}$. The function

$\nu_d = \nu_d \left(\frac{f_{co}}{E_{lat}} \right)$ is independent on scale and concrete strength, but depends on confinement properties (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Asymptotic DPR and Poisson ratio plotted in one graph for carbon and basalt confinements. Open symbols – DPR, closed symbols – Poisson ratio. Solid line – approximation.

From data of basalt confinement the formula (2) is modified:

$$E_2 = 6.19 E_{lat} \cdot \left(\frac{f_{co}}{E_{lat}} \right)^{0.44} \quad (2^1)$$

3) Immediately from (2) or (2¹) and Figure 1 follows the formula for ultimate axial strain

$$\varepsilon_{cc} = \varepsilon_{co} + \frac{f_{cc} - f_{co}}{E_2},$$

which can be rewritten for carbon and basalt confinement:

$$\varepsilon_{cc} = \varepsilon_{co} + 0.17 \cdot (\varepsilon_{ju} - \nu_o \varepsilon_{co}) \left(\frac{E_{lat}}{f_{co}} \right)^{0.65} \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{cc} = \varepsilon_{co} + 0.65 (\varepsilon_{ju} - \nu_o \varepsilon_{co}) \left(\frac{E_{lat}}{f_{co}} \right)^{0.44} \quad (3^1)$$

4) The tensile behavior of FRP material is characterized by linearly elastic stress-strain relationship until failure. The ultimate lateral stress in concrete is:

$$\sigma_{lu} = -E_{lat} \varepsilon_{ju}$$

where ε_{ju} - ultimate hoop strain of the FRP jacket. The realization of the fiber strength in a FRP highly depends on the fiber volume fraction, the mean fiber strength (fixed at a certain length), and the scatter of fiber strength [7] in composite. However, the manufacturer does not give the information on the strength of fibers and its scatter (the Weibull parameters). Therefore, the data given by the manufacturer cannot be used without correction and the ultimate hoop strain must be determined from special tests. The most suitable test was found to be the split-disk test to estimate the hoop properties of the FRP jacket. For the carbon FRP confinement the average ultimate hoop strain value from the split-disk test ε_{ju}^d was found to be only about 0.6 of the value given by the manufacturer ε_{ju}^m [1].

However, experimental results show that the ultimate hoop strain ε_{ju} measured directly in the confined concrete specimen test is even less than the ultimate hoop strain ε_{ju}^d determined from the split-disk test. This reduction can be explained by the following reasons:

- The quality of the FRP jacket – improperly aligned fibers, presence of the voids in the resin.
- Existence of localized deformations in the cracked concrete, which leads to a non-uniform stress distribution in the FRP jacket and hence premature failure of the jacket.

It was found in [1] that the ultimate hoop strain values from the confined specimen tests is significantly lower than the values obtained from the split disk test. The coefficient of reduction depends on the quality of the column surface and quality of wrapping of carbon composite. According numerous data the reduction lies between 0.9 and 0.6. Therefore the ultimate hoop strain of the carbon FRP jacket will be no less than:

$$\varepsilon_{ju} = 0.6 \cdot 0.6 \varepsilon_{ju}^m = 0.36 \varepsilon_{ju}^m.$$

Hereafter ε_{ju} will be the conservative value of the ultimate hoop strain of the FRP jacket which accounts for the above mentioned effects. (It should be noted, that reduction coefficient is only valid for CFRP confinement. The reduction factors for the aramid (AFRP) and glass (GFRP) confinement must be determined separately.)

In praxis only the columns reinforced by steel bars are used. But the steel bars start to yield when the stress level reaches the plain concrete strength. During yielding the elastic modulus of the steel bars is almost zero and they no more contribute to the stiffness of the column. The FRP jacket prevents the buckling of the yielding steel bars until the failure of the specimens.

Fig. 3. Compressive behavior of confined concrete columns with (1) and without (2) steel bar reinforcement.

Consequently the formula for the strength of confined reinforced columns f_{cc} looks as:

$$f_{ccr} = f_{co} + \frac{4\sigma_{ju}h}{R} + n_s f_y \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^2, \quad (4)$$

where r is the radius of steel bars, n – the number of steel bars, f_y – yield stress of steel [4].

Fig. 4. Buckling of steel bar reinforcement

- 5) It is seen from Figure 1 that $\frac{E_2}{E_1} \ll 1$. Therefore the danger of the confined column instability appears when the axial stress exceeds f_{cc} . In [5] the analysis of instability of confined columns was carried out and it was found that confinement is effective only for columns of moderate slenderness ($\lambda < 40$).

Fig. 5. Predicted and experimentally obtained values of the critical stress as a function of the slenderness.

Closed symbols – results from the confined specimen tests, Solid line – prediction of the critical stress. Line 1 - Euler's hyperbola, where $E_1=E_2$. Line 2 - Euler's hyperbola, where $E_1=E_1$.

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